

PARENT- TEACHER EXTENT OF INVOLVEMENT IN THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE V - RAMON MAGSAYSAY OF BAGONG NAYON II ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN THE NEW NORMAL SCHOOL YEAR 2020-2021, BASES FOR A PROPOSED INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The face-to-face conduct of classes has come to its end in schools and community learning center due to the Covid 19 pandemic. This is one of the biggest problems we encountered in most part of the regions in the country. The government take measures from health protocols, physical distancing, and community quarantine to contain the spread of the virus. The proponent conducted this study because one of the sectors greatly affected by this corona virus is education. This study aimed to determine the extent of parent- teacher involvement in the academic performance of Grade 5 section Ramon Magsaysay of Bagong Nayon II Elementary School. The researcher used a descriptive study utilized quantitative research method. Purposive sampling was used and conducted via online through google forms. Checklist- questionnaire was sent through group chat of 34 parents-pupils and 26 teachers. Standard procedures were used to process and represent findings. The statistical treatment used were percentage, weighted mean, and t-test. Results showed that there is a significant different between parent- teacher conference through distribution of modules and retrieval of outputs, while the second aspect shows that there is no significant different in participation in school performance task. Lastly, it showed that there is a significant difference in the perceptions of parent and teachers in pupil's supervision during new normal. In addition to the academic performance of pupils, results showed that the average grade level of pupils from first quarter to second quarter is positively high. This implies that there is a positive significant relationship between parent and teacher in the academic performance of pupils in the

new normal. Moreover, parents and teachers were able to adapt to the new trend in educating children following the intervention program.

Keywords: *academic performance, community quarantine, corona virus, covid-19 pandemic, health protocols, parental involvement*

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this research is to gather more information on parental involvement in education. In doing so, the researcher hopes to learn and grow from the information gathered by this study during the new normal. By doing this research study, information concerning parents and teachers and their own practices in the classroom and at home are obtained. This information enables the teachers/ researchers to observe the dynamics of their own classroom, while investigating how to develop parental involvement in their pupils' education.

According to Secretary Briones (2020) the "New Normal" in the system of education was creating a brave new world and we must start within the children to give them courage, to give them initiative, to help them look at problems realistically, and to continually have hope and confidence that we will overcome this situation. The so-called new normal becomes a battle cry for both parents and teachers. Serving pupils in different ways just like it used to be had a big impact on the quality education that the pupils deserved. Using self-learning modules and other instructional materials can pave the way much of the burden of parents. For some cases that parents find it difficult to understand the content of its module as well as the instruction written there the teacher can provide self-made instructions which is related to the given choices. Open communication and willingness to adjust for both parents and teachers considering the situations we are into it can see a real change within a new normal. The education agencies and schools scrambled to create fool-proof policies on governance structure, teacher management, and student management. Teachers, who were used to conventional teaching delivery, were also obliged to embrace technology despite their lack of technological literacy. To address this problem, online learning webinars and peer support systems were launched. Specifically, not all pupils were able to focus on the online classes because of the availability of the internet at home. This is the reason why some students did not come up with the new demand of technology. On the part of the students, dropout rates increased due to economic, psychological, and academic reasons (Franchi, 2020).

Parental involvement is the main factor in the full achievement of children from beginning to end their support in the school activities matters to them (Bartolome et al., 2017). Indeed, parental engagement plays a vital role in the academic achievement of students (Lara & Saracostti, 2019). With the COVID-19 pandemic different modalities was introduced and this became a part of teaching and learning process. Parents were the ones who supported children in the new normal (Daniela et al., 2021). In March 2020,

Allego said the 27.2 million of students were affected due to corona virus and even the closure of educational system. In the hope of the strict implementation of varying community quarantine put into action by a newly created and unified government body called IATF-IED (Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases). According to UNESCO in one of their reports, there were about 1.2 billion learners worldwide and about 28 million in the Philippines alone instructed to go home and around the month of March 2020 as there were a steady rise in the total number of cases, especially those that included death statistics (DOH, 2020).

Moreover, Toquero, (2020) mentioned that parent's involvement during pandemic is important because the new policies were embraced and through parents they need to provide and support them. He also mentioned the necessity and the necessary changes in the teaching "tools" to abide by this new approach of teaching-learning system thrust to without much question on 'readiness much so of appropriate and relevant trainings. Despite the obstacle being experienced the whole community was able to address some problems pertaining to the academic solutions. Chung et al. (2020), an associate professor in UITM, conducted research and reported that lessons, projects, group work, presentations, and evaluations were created and implemented using technology whereas online classes are the best solution in ensuring quality education in the new norm since most of the interactions happened online. Educators had to stay positive in the face of these rapid changes and prepare classes with urgent notices, but many pupils and students found it struggling to learn online. As online learning should be implemented by educators during the Covid-19 outbreak (to restrict student movement), and because it is being implemented for the first time by educators, some researchers have identified opportunities to investigate the challenges faced by educators and learners in online teaching and learning (Bibi Noraini & Jihan, 2020). As stated by Preeti, (2020) education greatly affected by pandemic it led to closure of schools and institutions. This also led to embrace the use of different technology.

Furthermore, Osman (2020), different challenges were encountered in assessing and evaluating learners' performance in online learning for both parents and educators is concerns. Most of learners' assessments are conducted online, with educators, learners, and parents experiencing trial and error, ambiguity, and misunderstanding. The pandemic did not stop the creation of innovative way of giving quality education among learners. With the help of these online platform like group chat via messenger, google forms, enhancement activities or games, email, google meet and zoom education became easy access to the struggling nation. It served as an eye opener that learning is fun and interchangeably. With the adaption of the new curriculum the most essential learning competencies highlighted the system of education in the Philippines creating globally competitive individuals.

Research Questions

The researcher sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of parents and teachers' involvement in the academic performance of grade V- Ramon Magsaysay of Bagong Nayon II Elementary School in the new normal in terms of the following aspects?
 - a. Parent- teacher conference through distribution of modules and retrieval of outputs
 - b. Participation in school performance task
 - c. Pupil's Supervision during new normal
2. Is there a significant difference between the perception of parents and teachers in the extent of their involvement in academic performance of grade V- Ramon Magsaysay in the new normal?
3. What is the level of academic performance of the pupils as revealed by their general average during first and second quarter?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of parents and teachers in the extent of their involvement in academic performance of grade V- Ramon Magsaysay in the new normal?
5. What intervention program may be proposed to enhance the involvement of parents and teachers on academic performance in the new normal?

METHODOLOGY

The study determined the 34 parents and 26 teachers and 34 pupils of grade V- Ramon Magsaysay which included three aspects whereas the performance was based on the respond of parent and grade 5 teachers of Bagong Nayon II Elementary School in the school year 2020-2021.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Parent- Teacher and Pupil Respondents

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
Parent	34	36.17
Teacher	26	27.66
Pupil	34	36.17
Total	94	100

As shown in table 1, parent respondents are composed of 34 or 36.17 percent, while teacher respondents is composed of 26 or 27.66 percent, and pupil respondents is 34 or 36.17. The distribution of the respondents were the parents and pupils of Grade 5 Ramon Magsaysay as well as the 26 Grade 5 teachers.

a. Data Gathering Methods

The data gathering instruments that was used in this study is the questionnaire-checklist. This shall be developed by the researcher, checked, and later validated by five Master teachers from Bagong Nayon II Elementary School which are not part of the respondent.

The questionnaire dealt with the parent- teacher involvement with respect to distribution of modules and retrieval of outputs, participation in school performance task and pupils' supervision during the new normal. These aspects covered a total of 30 items which were distributed equally in the three mentioned aspects.

b. Data Analysis Plan

The method of research to be used in the study is the descriptive type. The data to be gathered will be tested statistically through weighted mean which determine the parent- teacher involvement in the academic performance of pupils. The t- test will be used to find out if there is significant different between the respondent. The percentage will be used on the performance of the pupils in academic subject.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows that Likert Scale is used to interpret the data on the extent of parents and teacher's involvement on pupils' academic performance of Grade V- Ramon Magsaysay.

Table 2
Likert Scale, Range and Verbal Interpretation

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent (VHE)
4	3.40 – 4.19	High Extent (HE)
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderate Extent (ME)
2	1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent (LE)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent (VLE)

Table 3

As reflected in table 3, with respect to the parent-teacher conference through distribution of modules and retrieval of outputs the over- all weighted mean for parent respondent have obtained 3.41 which is verbally interpreted as HIGH EXTENT. While the teacher respondent obtained 4.24 which interpreted as VERY HIGH EXTENT.

The findings imply that the parents should do everything for the welfare of their children to strive harder that lead them to a better academic achievement in the new normal.

Table 4

As shown in Table 4 with respect to the participation in school performance task the over- all weighted mean for parent respondents obtained 3.05 which is verbally interpreted as MODERATE EXTENT. While the teacher respondents obtained 3.35 which interpreted as MODERATE EXTENT.

This implies that parents recognize the importance of their participation in school performance task but still need to cooperate often to the teachers.

Table 5

It could be gleaned from the table 5 that the pupils’ supervision during new normal with the over-all weighted mean for parent respondents obtained 3.20 interpreted as MODERATE EXTENT. While the teacher respondents obtained 4.41 which were interpreted as VERY HIGH EXTENT.

This result shows that parents and teachers should highly observe their supervision during the new normal. This implies that the more concern and care for the children will have, the more they become enthusiastic in their studies despite this pandemic.

The Significant Difference between the Perceptions of Parent and Teacher Respondents in the Extent of their Involvement with Respect to the above-mentioned aspects

Table 6 presents the result of the test on the significant difference in the perception of the parent and teacher respondents with respect to the different aspects.

Table 6**a. Parent- teacher conference through distribution of modules and retrieval of outputs**

Respondent	N	Mean	Z _{computed} Value	Z _{critical} Value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
Parent	34	3.41	2.14	± 1.96	Reject the Ho	Significant
Teacher	26	4.24				

Legend: n – number of samples, Ho – Null hypothesis

In Table 6, computed z value is 2.14. As the computed z value is greater than the critical z value of 1.96 at level of significance of 5%, then the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is enough evidence to support the claim that there is a significant difference between the perceptions on the extent of parent teacher conference through distribution of modules and retrieval of outputs.

Table 7**b. Participation in school performance task**

Respondent	N	Mean	Z _{computed} Value	Z _{critical} Value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
Parent	34	3.05	1.11	± 1.96	Do not Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teacher	26	3.35				

In Table 7, computed z value is 1.11. As the computed z value is less than the critical z value of 1.96 at level of significance of 5%, then the statistical decision is do not reject the null hypothesis. This shows that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of parent and teacher in the extent of participation in school performance task

Table 8**c. Pupil's Supervision during new normal**

Respondent	N	Mean	Z _{computed} Value	Z _{critical} Value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
Parent	34	3.20	3.21	± 1.96	Reject the Ho	Significant
Teacher	26	4.41				

As seen in Table 8, at 5% level of significance, the critical z values are -1.96 and 1.96, and the computed z value is 3.21. Since the computed z value is greater than the critical z value of 1.96 as presented and then the decision is to reject the null hypothesis.

This implies that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of parent and teacher in pupil's supervision during the new normal.

The Level of Academic Performance of the Pupils as Revealed by their Average Grade

Table 9

Grade Ave. Grade	1	%	2	%	3	%	4	%	5	%	6	%	Total	%
Fairly Satisfactory (75 - 79)	2	25	1	11.11	3	37.5	2	33.33	0	0	0	10	8	23.53
Satisfactory (80 - 84)	3	37.5	4	44.44	3	37.5	1	16.67	1	50	1	100	13	38.23
Very Satisfactory (85 - 89)	1	12.5	2	22.22	2	25	1	16.67	1	50	0	0	7	20.59
Outstanding 91-100	2	25	2	22.22	0	0	2	33.33	0	0	0	0	6	17.65
Total	8	100	9	100	8	100	6	100	2	100	1	100	34	100

As shown on the table 9, the highest rating obtained by the pupils during the first and second grading period using descriptive grade is 38.23 percent of 80-84 equivalent to Satisfactory, while 17.65 percent of 85-89 equivalent to Outstanding and 23.53 percent of 75-79 is Fairly Satisfactory and 20.59 percent of Very Satisfactory. The results imply that the level of academic performance of pupils from first grading to second grading have significantly passing scores.

This implies that the pupils are performing well in their academic endeavors in school since they feel that they are taken care of, monitored, and properly manage by their parents during the new normal.

The Significant Difference between the Level of Academic Performance of the Pupils in the First and Second Grading Periods

Table 10 presents the level of academic performance of the pupil during first grading and second grading periods.

Table 10
Summary of Computations in the Level of Academic Performance of the Pupil in the First and Second Grading Periods Using Paired t Test

Grading Period	Mean	Sd	t_{computed} Value	t_{critical} Value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=118$)	Decision	Interpretation
First	83.52	2.65	-2.81	± 1.98	Reject the H_0	Significant
Second	84.60	2.45				

As seen in Table 10, at 5% level of significance and 118 degrees of freedom, the critical t values are -1.98 and 1.98, and the computed t value is -2.81. Since the computed t value is less than the critical t value of -1.98 as presented, then the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is sufficient evidence to support the claim that there is a significant difference between the levels of academic performance of the pupil in the first and second grading periods.

Table 11

Table 11 shows that the average grade of pupils in the first grading period is 83.52 and 84.6 in the second grading period with mean difference of 1.08. This means that parents and teachers have similar perception regarding the effects of parental involvement on the academic performance of the pupils. This implies that both respondents are aware of the roles of parents in supporting children's school performances during this time of pandemic.

This also implies that parental involvement is significantly related to pupil's academic performance. This is parallel to the findings of Gordon (2009) that parental involvement has direct and positive relation to the performance of the pupil.

Conclusions:

- 1 Pupils are often closely monitored by their parents at home in the new normal. Likewise, parents usually participate in school related activities during distribution and retrieval of outputs.
- 2 Parent- Teacher involvement and pupils' academic performance are significantly related.
- 3 Parents and pupils have similar views regarding the extent of parent-teacher involvement for improving pupil's academic performance despite pandemic.

Recommendations:

The following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Parents and teachers should have close coordination on pupil's performance to institute remedial measures especially those parents at work in leaning modular distance learning.
2. Strengthen the networking of the school with the LGU's and NGOs to gain financial support for school programs and projects especially now that strong connection is needed.
3. Schedule regular family day, programs, online kumustahan and other occasional celebrations to enhance strong ties of teachers and parents.
4. The action plan for parental involvement is highly recommended for implementation.
5. Similar studies maybe conducted considering other variables.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured compliance with obtaining informed consent, respected the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, maintained their anonymity and safeguarded their well- being.

The researcher also ensured that there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study, strictly avoided the plagiarism, and upheld objectivity in the interpretation of the data

The researcher understands that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were purely used for research.

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REFERENCES

- Allego, Rafelle (August 2020). Totally “unprepared”: The Philippines’ education system is buckling under Covid-19. Retrieved from <https://www.arianalife.com/topic-type/news-feature/totally-unprepared-thephilippines-education-system-is-buckling-under-covid-19>
- Bartolome, M. T., Mamat, N., & Masnan, A. H. (2017). Parental involvement in the Philippines: A review of literatures. *Southeast Asia Early Childhood Journal*, 6, 41-50. <https://doi.org/10.37134/saecj.vol6.5.2017>
- Bibi Noraini, M. Y., & Jihan, A. (2020). Are We Prepared Enough? A Case Study of Challenges in Online Learning in a Private Higher Learning Institution during the Covid-19 Outbreaks. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 7, 205-212. <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.75.8211>
- Chung, E., Subramaniam, G., & Dass, L. C. (2020). Online Learning Readiness among University Students in Malaysia amidst Covid-19. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 16, 46-58. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v16i2.10294>
- Daniela, L., Rubene, Z., & Rudolfa, A. (2021). Parents’ perspectives on remote learning in the pandemic context. *Sustainability*, 1(7), 3640. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13073640>
- DepEd. (2020). Official Statement Department of Education. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/06/24/briones-education-ministers-unite-to-ensure-learning-continuity-amid-covid-19/>
- DOH. (2020). Department of Health Philippines. Retrieved on 28 November 2020 from <http://www.doh.gov.ph/2019-nCoV>

- Franchi, T. (2020). The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on current anatomy education and future careers: A student's perspective. *Anatomical Sciences Education*, 13(3), 312–315.
- Lara, R., & Saracostti, M. (2019). Effect of parental involvement on children's academic achievement in Chile. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1464
- Osman, M. E. (2020). Global Impact of Covid-19 on Education Systems: The Emergency Remote Teaching at Sultan Qaboos University. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 46, 463-471.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2020.1802583>
- Preeti, T. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Education System. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29, 3812-3814.
- Toquero, C. M. (2020). Challenges and Opportunities for Higher Education amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Philippine Context. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4), em0063.
<https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/7947>
- UNESCO. (2020). COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>